

CONDITIONS OF THE PROCESS OF FORMING THE SKILLS AND COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES IN PRACTICAL LESSONS

M. Mamajanova ¹

(Scientific Supervisor: Senior teacher of SamSIFL Ibadova N.A.)

Abstract:

This study examines the essential conditions necessary for the effective formation of skills and competencies among students with disabilities during practical lessons. With a focus on inclusive education, the research delves into the diverse needs and challenges faced by this student demographic in educational settings. Drawing on a comprehensive review of literature, this paper identifies key factors such as accessible learning materials, specialized teaching methods, adaptive technologies, and supportive learning environments as crucial elements for successful skill development. The role of educators, curriculum adaptations, and inclusive practices in education and the promotion of equal opportunities for all learners, regardless of their abilities. "New Uzbekistan 2022-2026 years on the strategy of development "decree" on the formation of an effective system of puddling and strengthening of those with disabilities, their quality of life and increasing the scope of the specified purpose and tasks in the context of the dam. In order to improve the system of inclusive education and employment, ensuring the involvement and active participation of a person with disabilities in the socioeconomic life of society, work was carried out in educational institutions of the republic. In addition, the issues of implementing a system of methodological and educational support for the training of students with disabilities were touched upon. In this article, some problems of teaching disabled students and possible ways of solving them will be enlightened.

Key words: students with disabilities, higher inclusive education, with a violation of the musculoskeletal system, process engineer, practical training, methodology, educational and methodological support, distance learning

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Future specialists in a number of leading Higher Educational Institutions of the world ensuring continuity and continuity of education in the preparation process in order to combine traditional and distance forms of teaching attention is paid to the use of the case. The USA, Russia, and Great Developed countries such as Britain and South Korea have higher education special to the education of students with disabilities in the system attention is given. It is traditional in the higher inclusive education of states in addition to education, distance (open electronic) education systems it is effectively functioning in this regard. To this end, in the ATMs, training of students with disabilities (impaired musculoskeletal system) Organization of the process, their practical skills in the

¹ Mamajanova. M.G', student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

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lessons and formation of skills, from advanced pedagogical technologies development of methodological models regarding the process of use, clarification of the psychological and pedagogical properties of teaching and implementation of the selection of optimal training options in the educational process more attention is paid to research aimed at increasing. And this can be used in educational institutions of the technical direction- skills and abilities of technologists in practical training formation and improvement on the basis of modern approaches higher an important factor in raising the quality of education to a new level. In the practice of many leading foreign countries with disabilities innovative approaches to teaching and educating students, generally through the formation of a system of knowledge, technical design in them of such important professional qualities as integrability and competitiveness there is an opportunity to form practical drawings. For this reason, teaching students with disabilities, teaching and study from a psychological, and medical point of view and favourable conditions for them great research from the leadership of the CPSU and pedagogical teachers in the creation requires [3].

Improving the quality level of Personnel Training in the Republic, training of highly qualified specialists based on international standards, education advanced pedagogical process based on international standards extensive reforms on the introduction of technologies quality-effectiveness of training in higher educational institutions as a result training of qualified professional personnel is relevant for the increase. In particular, Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the development strategy, the formation of an effective system of adaptation of persons with disabilities, their quality of life and increasing the level of: non-discrimination on the sign of disability, disability rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of persons who are for the realization of equal conditions and their violation ensuring the inevitability of responsibility; in the field of ensuring the rights of persons with disabilities to national legislation recognized international norms and standards implementation; transparent medical and labour examination and disability determination, introduction of modern style and criteria, with disabilities the level and quality of medical and social assistance to persons increase; interaction with the family, society and the state of persons with disabilities strengthen communication, their presence in a comfortable environment, City passenger free of Transportation, social and other infrastructure facilities create the necessary conditions for use; socio-economic life of society of persons with disabilities inclusive education and employment providing involvement and active participation improvement of the placement system; step-by-step transition to the social model of disability determination tasks such as defined [1].

This is evident from the set goals and objectives, decent support in society for persons with disabilities is one of the priority tasks of our state. Formation of the educational and material base of universities, which is necessary to providing technical means, and effective practical training Organization of activities of students with disabilities is one of the priority tasks of laying. By our government 2021- 2023 in 81 buildings and structures of ATMs construction, reconstruction, overhaul and equipment works at these facilities, it is planned to create all favourable conditions for students with disabilities, both internal and external, of the buildings of the University students with disabilities in the musculoskeletal system in the corridors comply with the requirements of the norm at the entrance points for safe movement ramps, handrails, special (tactile

tilled) aisles and upper elevator or lift corridors to climb floors as well as the first it is clearly determined that separate special toilets will be erected on the floors given. Developed for training highly qualified personnel and based on the experience and conditions of foreign universities undergraduate education areas qualification requirements, curriculum and programs modernization and improvement of content, advanced to educational practice implementation of ZPs and ICTs of foreign experiments, e-learning creation of modules, multimedia developments, electronic education development of platforms and introduction of electronic forms of training improving the quality of education through the establishment of quality personnel particular attention is paid to the preparation. Including those with disabilities using ICT opportunities in teaching students Organization of training work and its software it is important to create and fill it with didactic work.

Conducting practical classes in the organization of the educational process to form a system of generalized knowledge of students will help. In the technical direction, the Universities of the National Sciences specially equipped when carrying out practical training, project work using the capabilities of ICT in audiences, modern organization using educational technologies and techniques gives an effective result [5]. Practical in general subjects of students with disabilities "Blended learning" and "Flipped learning" in the organization of classes through the application of educational technologies and "project" techniques such as it is advisable to form practical skills and abilities in them will. The purpose of technology: to educate teachers and students in the educational process to prevent exhaustion, less effort, knowledge in science, it consists in the formation of skills, qualifications and personality qualities. "Blended learning" technology offers students the following opportunities gives: offline and online at any time with training material familiarization; performance of practical training in audiology; test tests test your knowledge by submitting; audio and video recordings, animation and using simulations; using E-mail and on forums participation; Organization of communication between the teacher-student and students. While "Flipped learning" is a form of Education, that transfers the passive movement of recipients to a new look concept. As an educational homework in this education sees practical training and is practical in the audience with the teacher performs assignments. Improving the quality, effectiveness of education in modern conditions in order to increase the use of these technologies is extremely important it is considered. "Project" as interactive techniques in practical training, it is advisable to use the method. The "project" method involves planning more complex practical tasks and who acquire knowledge and practical skills in the process of implementation is a training system. The project method is always active in students focused on independent practical work; they are for a certain period of time they do.

The purpose of Project-Based Learning: student development creating conditions for the acquisition of non-acquired knowledge from various sources; study-knowledge of the acquired knowledge and in solving practical problems learning to use; their design and research skills develops; systemic thinking, attention, imagination and memory enhances [4]. Implement the goals and objectives set in the development strategy education of modern educational technologies and techniques in increasing it will be appropriate to widely promote and put into practice the process. The methodology used was disabled in practical training service for the formation of practical skills and abilities of students and all higher education in the technical direction from this

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methodology good result in the use of subjects in the teaching of general subjects gives.

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